

Children negotiating meanings in kidfluencers' channels

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ABSTRACT

YouTube is a commercialised digital environment that provides profitable opportunities for content creators. Children's channels have proliferated in recent years on this platform. Children YouTubers become kidfluencers when they reach an important number of subscriptions and brands start to show interest in their channels. Following a qualitative methodology with focus groups, in which 263 primary education pupils participated, we examined these pupils' use of social media and their relationships with the influencers followed, together with their media literacy skills and negotiation of meanings upon watching a Spanish kidfluencer's channel. Pupils were encouraged to express and communicate their experiences, thoughts, feelings and opinions about these YouTubers' messages through peer interaction. The results point to an early overexposure to digital content and social media; the consumption of content aimed at young adults and unsuitable for their ages; variable media competence due to the children's developmental level; and negotiated and oppositional readings in the reception of these kidfluencers' messages.

Keywords: *YouTube, kidfluencers, social media consumption, media competence, negotiated and oppositional reading, primary education pupils.*

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INTRODUCTION

Social media platforms are spaces where ordinary users can participate by way of creating their own content, engaging with audiences and interacting with other users. Among these platforms, YouTube, in particular, has become a global cultural phenomenon with billions of users. It must be remembered that video traffic is the highest percentage of all global circulation on the Internet (Renés Arellano, Gozávez Pérez & Berlanga Fernández, 2020). YouTube includes all the audio-visual technological advances and all the social media affordances (profiles, subscriptions, likes, comments, share, etc.), and is a clear example of the heavily commercialised digital environment (Jorge, Marôpo & Nunes, 2018; Marôpo, Jorge & Tomaz, 2020) that exists under the business model of the attention economy. In consonance with various authors' views (Jordan & Klein, 2020; Livingstone, 2020; Palatino, 2020), we could argue that the Internet seems to have moved away from the utopia of global connection and free access to knowledge to become a powerful tool in surveillance capitalism.

YouTube generates income through on-site advertising and it pays a percentage to partner channels. It encourages users to create 'profitable' content whilst giving them support and advice, and also helping them to make their channel grow and to monetarise their contents (Tur-Viñes, Núñez-Gómez & Martínez-Pastor, 2019). Furthermore, the platform gathers data in order to personalise the users' experience and to adapt recommendations. Moreover, as Márquez and Ardévol (2018) explain, it also offers YouTubers the possibility of associating themselves with multi-channel networks. Such networks act as representatives of YouTubers, managing their career and negotiating the conditions of their contracts with brands. Many of these networks have been acquired by large media corporations such as Maker studios, which forms part of the Disney Corporation. Following Márquez and Ardévol (2018), we can affirm that audiences are therefore commodified and their attention is sought in order to be sold to advertisers; YouTubers need views, subscriptions and likes, and therefore the content they create has to be appealing and attractive.

The key to the continuing success of YouTubers and influencers rests on the notion of portraying themselves as authentic, natural, spontaneous (for example, preserving a 'homemade' format), reliable and intimate (for example, displaying areas of the home as main scenarios and revealing 'private' information) and

uninterested in success (López-Villafranca & Olmedo-Salar, 2019). They target their age group who in turn see them as equals and accessible (Castillo-Abdul, Romero-Rodríguez & Larrea-Ayala, 2020; Pérez-Torres, Pastor-Ruiz & Abarrou-Ben-Boubaker, 2018). They all use similar tactics to captivate their audiences, with similar narratives, orality, audio-visual expressiveness, and also similar ways of engaging with their audiences and establishing a relationship of closeness and trust (Márquez & Ardévol, 2018). As Jorge, Marôpo and Nunes (2018) argue, YouTube is a place of participation and, at the same time, self-commodification; of culture and commercialisation; of empowerment and exploitation of audiences; of hegemonic and counterhegemonic practices.

The social influence YouTubers exert has made this phenomenon an object of study and analysis. Thus, for example, the relationship that these influencers have with children is beginning to be scrutinised with regard to the children's exposure to harmful content, excessive promotion of consumer culture and use of child labour as digital content producers (López-Villafranca & Olmedo-Salar, 2019). As Livingstone states (2020):

Not only are children left to their own devices in a space conceived of as for adults, but also the digital environment is designed to amplify certain actions in accordance not with the best interests of the child but with commercial interests. Algorithms are optimised to recommend ever more extreme contents — whether stereotyped visions of perfect faces and perfect lives or, if you ever show an interest, escalating images of self-harm, violence or hate. Again, social norms lag behind technological developments. (p.3)

Algorithms are designed to recommend those videos that have attracted a greater audience share. Consequently, the younger the children are, the higher the likelihood of them following the recommendations displayed as thumbnail images and watching those popular videos (Jaakkola, 2020).

Kidfluencers and followers

Children's channels have proliferated on YouTube and not only have they proliferated but are among the most popular ones with overwhelming numbers of followers, subscriptions and views. As Jaakkola (2020) states, "children's entertainment has grown massively on YouTube [...] children are a large growing audience because they start using YouTube at a very early age [...]. All these channels have far greater audiences than traditional children's television programs" (pp. 237-238). In family homes, the Internet is used as a digital

pacifier that keeps children occupied while adult family members are busy with their daily duties (Jaakkola, 2020). Furthermore, kidfluencers' videos are available on YouTube Kids, which parents will deem to be a safe media environment (De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019). It is worth noting that in Spain there are more than 1,300 YouTube channels aimed at children, generating more than 5.6 billion views per month. Besides, the ten most popular YouTube channels in Spain are for children. Between the ages of two and five, 64% of Spanish children already use YouTube, and from the ages of six and seven they begin to follow influencers' channels¹. Moreover, Spain has a high number of globally successful kidfluencers (Vizcaino-Laorga, Martínez Pastor & Serrano Maillo, 2019).

Among these children's channels, we can find different genres and formats such as unboxing, toy reviews, vlogs, gaming, challenges, tutorials, etc. YouTube has become one of the most profitable platforms as a result of investment from advertising and due to its ability to attract children who are of great interest to advertisers (López-Villafranca, & Olmedo-Salar, 2019, p. 2). Children are active consumers; they also influence adults' consumption decisions, and at the same time they are future consumers (Buckingham, 2011; De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019), "commercial or promotional content has become a naturalized and acceptable component in even those communication environments where younger people spend their time" (Jaakkola, 2020, p. 240).

More often than not, child YouTubers begin as amateur producers, creating videos with or without adults for pleasure and fun, and, in some cases, they develop themselves into professionals whereby they become kidfluencers. The professionalisation of these YouTubers takes place when the number of subscriptions to their channels increases and brands start to show interest in their channels. The implication of this is that their parents and/or companies will act as managers for them, in addition to the children managing the pressure of working. In this regard, it is unclear to what extent these children are protected by child labour laws (De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019; Tur-Viñes, Núñez-Gómez & Martínez-Pastor, 2019; Vizcaino-Laorga, Martínez Pastor & Serrano Maillo, 2019).

For these kidfluencers, this professionalisation also entails using different tactics to please their audiences

and to increase their number of followers. They all follow similar patterns and use similar methods as part of the global digital culture of YouTube, namely, humour and dramatisation; apparent spontaneity and authenticity; intimacy (intimate stories, exhibition of private scenarios, participation of family members, direct interaction); introduction of advertising in a 'natural' way; scripts with brief stories structured in start, nod and outcome sections; use of post-production techniques, etc. (Jaakkola, 2020; López-Villafranca & Olmedo-Salar, 2019; Marôpo, Jorge & Tomaz, 2020; Sánchez-Labela Martín, 2020). They become fictional characters, outgoing, cheerful, dynamic, creative, persuasive, active, enthusiastic and inventive, performing a script in order to offer their audiences and brands what they demand and, perhaps worryingly, these fictional identities are often riddled with stereotypes (Sánchez-Labela Martín, 2020).

These children, as kidfluencers, exert a certain type of impact on the socialisation of their followers, who also happen to be children themselves. Whilst watching their videos children acquire notions, values, beliefs, attitudes, behaviours, etc. (Marôpo, Jorge & Tomaz, 2020; Renés Arellano, Gozávez Pérez & Berlanga Fernández, 2020; Sánchez-Labela Martín, 2020). As Pérez-Torres, Pastor-Ruiz and Abarrou-Ben-Boubaker (2018) explain, YouTubers not only entertain but also act as models to follow and advisors on key issues related to their followers' identity construction, thereby performing a socialising function. Followers develop parasocial relationships with the kidfluencers (Aran-Ramspott, Fedele & Tarragó, 2018; De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019). They create an emotional connection of wishful identification with their favourite YouTubers (Tolbert & Drogos, 2019) establishing a friend-like relationship (Marôpo, Jorge & Tomaz, 2020). They consider them an essential source of information and try to imitate their lifestyles (Rasmussen, Riggs & Sauerlich, 2021).

In this context, these channels are now being subjected to analysis and criticism due to the exhibition, commodification and exploitation of children, the gathering of data (Lupton & Williamson, 2017) and the normalisation of monetising their private life and their identity from early ages (Jordan & Klein, 2020; Livingstone, 2020). López-Villafranca and Olmedo-Salar (2019) assert that parents do not appear to consider

¹ See: https://elpais.com/retina/2019/06/20/tendencias/1561012535_705158.html?event_log=oklogin and

<https://www.lavanguardia.com/edicion-impresa/20191014/47952600813/youtubers-infantiles-en-el-punto-de-mira.html>

the risks of this media exhibition, overexposing their children to what is presented as a business without advertising regulations and a representation of minors who show unreal worlds, inciting others to compulsive consumerism. There are concerns about the fact that these kidfluencers act as celebrity endorsers and their commercial messages are much more effective due to the credibility given by their audience (Martínez & Olsson, 2019). Moreover, advertising is introduced as part of the narrative, making it difficult to distinguish between content and publicity (Jaakkola, 2020; Sánchez-Labela Martín, 2020). The videos of these YouTubers are often scenes of product placement and product integration that are not explicitly indicated. These advertising techniques are less obtrusive and, therefore, more difficult to recognise. The commercial nature of most of these kidfluencers' videos is too often not appropriately disclosed (Choi, 2023; De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019). Besides, it is important to highlight that children under the age of twelve are especially vulnerable to advertising since their advertising literacy is not fully developed (Buijzen, Van Reijmersdal & Owen, 2010; De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019). Therefore, covert advertising tactics are based on deceit, since, on many occasions, neither the child YouTubers' followers, nor their parents, are aware of the influencers' intentions and are not able to recognise their selling techniques (Evans, Hoy & Childers, 2018; Núñez-Cansado, López-López & Somarriba-Arechavala, 2021; Pearce & Baran, 2018). Kidfluencers contribute to the commercialisation of children's everyday lives (Martínez & Olsson, 2019) and their persuasive messages can be considered unethical. As Pearce and Baran (2018) state, influencer marketing aimed at children makes them defenceless by way of treating them as non-persons and a mere means to satisfy the YouTubers' and companies' own profit motives.

Furthermore, there are worries about the counter-values (Renés Arellano, Gozávez Pérez & Berlanga Fernández, 2020) and reproduction of stereotypes. Among these stereotypes, gender ones stand out given the biased content display by male and female kidfluencers, both in the narratives and in the products advertised (Aznar Díaz, Trujillo Torres, Romero Rodríguez & Campos Soto, 2019). Male YouTubers'

channels are usually gameplays while most female ones fit in the lifestyle category (Castillo-Abdul, Romero-Rodríguez & Larrea-Ayala, 2020). Hence, Sánchez-Labela Martín (2020) explains that girl YouTubers portray themselves as being trapped by infatuation, fashion, makeup, often existing in a world of princesses or playing the role of housewives and caretakers. This is the case in *Las Ratitas'* channel, starring two sisters, aged 9 and 11. At the time of writing the channel occupies the 4th highest position of YouTubers in Spain with 24.8M subscribers and 9,350,289,681 video views², and they have maintained this position for several years (Castillo-Abdul, Romero-Rodríguez & Larrea-Ayala, 2020). They started appearing on YouTube in 2015, when they were just 3 and 5 and, nowadays, they also have another YouTube channel called Saneub, Instagram, Facebook and TikTok accounts. They also participate in their parents' social media sites. *Las Ratitas'* channel follows the same patterns as other young YouTubers: their videos are usually striking, colourful and noisy; they have catchy titles; they use a high and emphatic tone, with an unnatural and even strident effect; they display private scenarios, mainly the exterior and interior of their home; they have deactivated comments; the advertising and product placement is embedded in their narratives; they use pre and post-production techniques; they represent a happy, idyllic, fairy-tale, pink world and are always surrounded by gender-biased toys (Castillo-Abdul, Romero-Rodríguez & Larrea-Ayala, 2020; Núñez-Cansado, López-López & Somarriba-Arechavala, 2021; Sánchez-Labela Martín). *Las Ratitas'* channel³ has been denounced on the grounds of child exploitation and gender stereotypes.

This study aims to shed light on children's perceptions and appropriation of meanings in kidfluencers' channels, such as *Las Ratitas*. Our interest in delving into the possible influence exerted by these types of channels stems from two perceived needs in the related research. Firstly, as Tur-Viñes, Núñez-Gómez and Martínez-Pastor (2019) explain in their systematic review of existing studies on the topic of young YouTubers, most studies focus on the content analysis of videos, with little research having been undertaken in relation to children's perceptions. Concerning the methodological aspects, Tur-Viñes, Núñez-Gómez and Martínez-Pastor (2019) affirm that most studies follow

² <https://socialblade.com/youtube/c/lasratitas>

³ https://www.huffingtonpost.es/2019/02/19/denuncian-a-un-canal-de-youtube-de-dos-ninas-por-promover-estereotipos-de-genero_a_23672662/

a qualitative methodology with an average of 39.5 participants. Our study is also a qualitative piece of research but considerably expands the number of participating subjects, as we will see below. Secondly, many studies have focused on aspects related to influencer marketing and persuasion processes in relation to children (Buijzen; Van Reijmersdal & Owen, 2010; De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019), however, broader aspects related to children's media competence have not been examined.

Hence, this study has been carried out for the purpose of answering the following research questions:

Q1. What do children from the ages of 6 to 12 attending a Spanish infant and primary education state school watch on YouTube and other social media platforms?

Q2. What are their media literacy skills like in terms of their knowledge of the production processes, the codes of audio-visual language and the underlying ideology?

Q3. What are their processes of interaction with YouTubers like and how do they read *Las Ratitas'* videos?

RESEARCH

Materials and method

This paper is the result of some of the findings of the project titled *Digital Childhood* (RTI 2018-093397-B-100)⁴, financed by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation. In phase 2 of this project, we carried out interviews with families for the purpose of having a better understanding of children's use of ICT at home. We discovered that families were concerned about the attraction that kidfluencers' channels, such as *Las Ratitas*, exert on their children:

[...] and I asked my daughter: Why do these girls (referring to *Las Ratitas*) have so many toys? And she says: Because they are cool mammy, they are cool, that is why they have so many toys. And then I have to explain to her... (Mother C2, 3:99)

These findings, together with the above-mentioned needs detected in the field, aroused our interest in carrying out the study we present in this paper, focusing on *Las Ratitas* as one of the most popular kidfluencers in Spain.

Following a qualitative methodology, we conducted focus groups with primary education pupils, aged 6 to 12. We wanted to encourage children to express and communicate their experiences, thoughts and feelings through peer interaction, thereby getting an in-depth understanding of how children engage with media, perceive media messages and construct meanings around them. As Parker and Tritter (2006) explain, focus group discussions are a type of group interview where participants are encouraged to discuss a specific issue which they have in common in their lives. The aim is to unveil the underlined norms, beliefs and values related to the matter in question. It is also important to take into account that our role as researchers conducting these focus groups was one of facilitators and moderators of the dialogue among participants. Following Parker and Tritter (2006) our role was peripheral rather than centre-stage. The dynamic aspects of interaction within the group was the focal point, given that it is this interaction which makes focus groups a powerful method for generating insight into a particular issue.

In order to encourage the desired interaction and dialogue among the pupils, we selected and watched with them two of the most popular videos in *Las Ratitas'* channel, one titled *McDonalds CON MI COCHE DRIVE THRU* (Fig. 1) and another one titled *Morning routine. LAVAS DIENTES, COMER Y JUGAR* (Fig. 2).

Pupils were encouraged to speak freely and express their opinions and we only introduced some open questions when we needed to prompt the discussion (Bourne & Winstone, 2021). Participants were selected by accessibility as a result of the interest shown from a state school in the study. Informed consent was obtained from the school principal, the school board, teachers and parents. The protection of the participants' data was guaranteed in the research. In relation to the pupils themselves, researchers asked for their consent before starting the focus group. The researchers introduced themselves, informed the pupils about the aims of the project, explained that they were completely free to participate and they only had to talk if they wanted to, and they were also asked for their permission to be recorded in audio.

⁴ Favourable report Bioethics Committee of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain), USC code 21/2022.

McDonalds 🍔 CON MI COCHE 🚗
DRIVE THRU 🍷
803 M de visualizaciones · hace 5 años

Figure 1. *Video McDonalds CON MI COCHE DRIVE THRU*⁵

MORNING ROUTINE - LAVAR
DIENTES COMER Y JUGAR
300 M de visualizaciones · hace 5 años

Figure 2. *Video Morning routine. LAVAS DIENTES, COMER Y JUGAR*⁶

Data collection instruments

The sources of data in this study derive from twelve focus groups. The research was conducted during school attendance hours and a total of 263 pupils participated in the focus groups. Each group discussion lasted around 50 minutes and they were recorded in audio and transcribed. The focus groups were conducted by two researchers. After watching *Las Ratitas'* videos, each class group was divided into two sub-groups with one of the researchers recording and dynamising the debate for around 20 minutes.

The researchers followed a script with open questions. They encouraged the participation of all pupils, directing the questions to each one of them, but also ensured those who decided to remain silent were made to feel comfortable. They also tried to encourage dialogue and debate among the participants. The questions were based on the content of the videos chosen and influenced by previous research, in particular the articulated proposal of media competence dimensions and indicators drawn up by Ferrés and Pisticelly (2012). These open questions were adapted to the different age-groups. For the last 10-15 minutes the sub-groups joined together for a final debate based on the issues that arose in the sub-groups. We tried to balance the rigour of the

research and the recommended number of participants in focus groups (Hennink, 2007), with the teachers' interest in getting all the pupils involved in this activity to foster media literacy education (Table 1).

Data analysis

The process of analysis and codification of data included three interconnected processes, namely, coding, sequential interpretation and categorisation. We started with a holistic reading of the transcripts followed by the creation of an already established list of codes, based on the focus group questions and organised into categories and subcategories. Throughout the process of linking evidence to codes new categories and subcategories emerged. The analysis of the previous and emergent codes, categories and subcategories, allowed for the identification of a series of topics related to media diet, media competence dimensions and indicators and media 'readings' (Table 2).

FINDINGS

What do these children watch on YouTube and other social media platforms?

Most pupils who participated in the focus groups affirmed that they watch videos on YouTube on a regular basis, and watch them on their own devices, in particular through the use of tablets (in each sub-group of all the focus groups only a small minority of pupils - 2 to 6 - remained silent, the rest participated and spoke of their regular use of YouTube). These results are in line with the data from the Qustodio 2022 annual report, which shows that in all countries analysed in the report "YouTube was the clear winner in terms of popularity" (Qustodio, 2023, p. 17). The type of videos the participants in the focus groups stated they watched were cartoons, videos related to their hobbies, funny videos, videos of challenges, videos related to doing handicrafts, and some of them mentioned that they watch videos to learn about things and to help them with their homework. Some said that they use YouTube a lot: "I watch millions of videos that I love [FG1.1A: 6:42]; I watch a lot of everything, everything I find" [FG3.1B: 8:13]. Very few pupils appeared to have viewing restrictions at home but they were not allowed to watch many things.

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pJLjueapaVw>
794.747.747 views, uploaded 16 August 2017.

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LqFyWd3fWNY>
299.914.615 views, uploaded 25 August 2017.

Table 1. *Data sources and examples*

Source	Code	Description	Sample questions to encourage reflection and debate
Focus group 1	FG1A	Year 1 primary education	Did you like this video? Why?
	FG1.1A	19 participants	
	FG1.2A	48', May 2022	
Focus group 2	FG1B	Year 1 primary education	Do you know <i>Las Ratitas</i> ?
	FG1.1B	22 participants	
	FG1.2B	52', May 2022	
Focus group 3	FG2A	Year 2 primary education	What do you think about the scene where the cat in the app is using the hairdryer whilst the air is blowing in the girls' direction?
	FG2.1A	20 participants	
	FG2.2A	50', May 2022	
Focus group 4	FG2B	Year 2 primary education	Is there anything you do not like in this video? What would you change?
	FG2.1B	21 participants	
	FG2.2B	47', May 2022	
Focus group 5	FG3A	Year 3 primary education	Do you follow any YouTubers?
	FG3.1A	25 participants	
	FG3.2A	49', May 2022	
Focus group 6	FG3B	Year 3 primary education	Why do you think these girls made this video?
	FG3.1B	24 participants	
	FG3.2B	52', May 2022	
Focus group 7	FG4A	Year 4 primary education	Are the girls playing or working?
	FG4.1A	23 participants	
	FG4.2A	51', May 2022	
Focus group 8	FG4B	Year 4 primary education	Who do you think invented the story of this video?
	FG4.1B	20 participants	
	FG4.2B	47', May 2022	
Focus group 9	FG5A	Year 5 primary education	Are they trying to sell us anything in this video?
	FG5.1A	19 participants	
	FG5.2A	54', May 2022	
Focus group 10	FG5B	Year 5 primary education	Do you think this video was easy to make?
	FG5.1B	24 participants	
	FG5.2B	51', May 2022	
Focus group 11	FG6A	Year 6 primary education	How do YouTubers earn money?
	FG6.1A	21 participants	
	FG6.2A	50', May 2022	
Focus group 12	FG6B	Year 6 primary education	Would a boy make a video with this story, or would he make something different? What kind of story would he choose?
	FG6.1B	25 participants	
	FG6.2B	51', May 2022	

Table 2. *Categories and subcategories with samples*

	Categories	Subcategories	Sample data evidence
FG2A	Media competence dimensions and indicators	Production processes	‘Their parents made it to earn money’ [7:34] ‘They earn money with the subscriptions’ [8:05] ‘They earn money and we enjoy ourselves’ [8:10]
FG5B	Media competence dimensions and indicators	Language	‘They do this with a hairdryer’ [10:26] ‘You can see that it is a trick but the little ones would believe it’ [11:09]
FG3B	Media competence dimensions and indicators	Ideology	‘It’s crazy, who wastes toilet paper like this? If they cut down so many trees, we run out of oxygen’ [23:12]
FG5B	Media ‘reading’	Oppositional reading	‘I would describe them as cheeky, greedy. They are spoilt [28:54]... I didn’t like anything. I find it very childish and fake [29:31]. Everything seems very prepared’ [31:25]
FG3B	Media diet	Followed YouTubers	‘I follow Compas, Invictor, Silvio Gamer [8:11]. ...Mondongo, Invictor, Sparta, Pled, El Magnum, here I can spend my life...[9:03] ...MikelTube, Compas [9:24], Laiaoli and Tekendo. Luan Palomera, Buho sabio [9:52]... Capitán gato...’[10:40]

They also claimed that they know and follow many YouTubers, including *Las Ratitas*. It appears that the ones who followed the greater number of YouTubers were 3rd year primary pupils (8-9 years of age), whereas the older pupils from years 5 and 6 (9 to 11 years of age) seemed to have moved on to TikTok and Twitch. The list of YouTubers mentioned most frequently were *Los Compas*, *Mikecrack*, *Invictor*, *El Trollino*, *FlexVega*, *Lyna*, *The Grefg*, *Arta Game*, *Mr Beast* or *Ibai Llanos*. These are all YouTubers with millions of subscribers, which indicates that, in general, they follow ‘popular’ influencers.

In addition, most of the YouTubers followed are adults, including many gamers and others that have entertainment channels with jokes and challenges. We perceived clear gender-based consumption trends with boys following male YouTubers such as *Mr Beast* or *Grefg*, while girls mentioned female YouTubers such as *Lyna* or *Laia Oli*. We should also remark that the videos in many of these YouTubers’ channels are a miscellanea of content, some of which could be suitable for these pupils’ ages while other content is clearly unsuitable and targeted at young adults.

Despite being familiar with *Las Ratitas*, only seven children of those who participated openly said that they currently watch *Las Ratitas*’ videos. The vast majority were of the opinion that their videos are ‘childish’ and that they now no longer watch the channel because they believe their videos are for kids, with even a boy from the 1st year claiming: “When I was 5 years old I used to watch them but now I’m 6 and I no longer watch them”

[FG1.2A: 18:03]. Some of them, in particular three girls and one boy, also stated that since their younger sisters or cousins watch them, they feel they ‘have to’ watch them with them.

Peer pressure was observed during the focus groups when some of them, particularly boys, started to mock the videos we showed and expressed that they disliked them, whilst others repeated their comments. Only one girl in one of the 4th year focus groups was willing to stand her ground by stating: “I liked the video and I’ve been following them since I was a kid and they don’t only do these things. I’m going to keep watching them, they are nice” [FG4B: 46:14]. Another two kidfluencers were mentioned in the dialogues, namely *MikeTube*, by a boy in the 2nd year, and *LeoTube* by a boy in the 1st year. However, as previously mentioned, adult YouTubers with a more adult like content seem to be the preferred choice for a large majority of these pupils.

Although most of these children were mere consumers of content created by others, some of them were also creators. Two boys from the 1st year had their own channel and three boys and one girl from 4th year also mentioned that they have a YouTube channel: “I have a channel and I make entertainment videos about funny things, I made one about Christmas gifts” [FG4A: 50:47]. In the 6th year two boys mentioned that they are streamers and that they started in YouTube but now they are in Twitch.

What are these children's media competence like?

Taking into account the dimensions and indicators of media competence (Ferrés & Piscitelli, 2012), the dialogues and debates in the focus groups showed that the children knew how to explain, rationalise and criticise the contents of the videos we showed. However, they did not control their emotions as they were clearly attracted to the stories. The analysis of their comments indicated that the media competence of these pupils, specifically in relation to their capacity to critically analyse the processes of production and the languages codes, was variable. We observed that the younger pupils, in particular first year pupils, were the ones with more difficulties identifying such things as the purpose of the video, the sponsorships, product placement and product integration, the processes of edition, or questioning whether these girls were actually working or playing, with most of them considering that they were playing. However, in both the 1st year groups there were a few pupils who expressed critical views making comments such as: "McDonalds gave them money to make this video... I would tell them to stop making videos to fool people" [FG1.1B: 34:22].

In general, all the pupils who participated, except for most of the first-year ones, seemed to be aware that the parents of these girls are behind the channel and videos, and that money is earned from them. They are aware that YouTubers earn money based on the number of subscribers they have. From year 2 pupils showed that they were perfectly aware that these two videos had been created to promote products. Two pupils also happened to mention that the video about *Talking Ginger* may have been produced because this game was famous at some stage and that other YouTubers were talking about it [FG3.1A: 30:12]. Although there remained some disagreement among the pupils as to whether these girls are playing or working, some pupils insisted that they are working, even suggesting they are clearly acting:

"I would like to know what these girls really do when they have finished recording a scene, whether they keep laughing and saying -this is really fun- or they say -this is boring- If they say the first things it's because they are playing, the parents earn money, and it's ok. But if they say that they are bored and don't want to continue, then they're working" [FG6.2A: 27:13].

Focusing on the pupils' media competence when it comes to 'reading' the codes of the audio-visual language, all the pupils who participated, except, once again, for most of the first-years, identified tricks used in one of the scenes from the video *Morning routine*

where the product is assigned features it does not have. However, pupils did not detect the trick until they were asked about it and when they became aware the following comments were made:

"[...] the water and the hairdryer, the father is doing it [...] But young children think it is true and then they are disappointed [...] It is a lie because they put a hairdryer in front of them [...] they are fooling people" [FG4.2B: 18:32]

Pupils were also critical about the title of this video stating that it did not have much to do with the story, "They gave it this title for parents [...] They gave it so people would click on it and then they add another visualisation [...] They put it to hide the ad" [FG6A.1: 22:05].

It is important to mention that those pupils who liked and followed *Las Ratitas*, having a kind of emotional connection with them, were less able to critically analyse these issues. A girl from the 4th year strongly defended them contradicting the opinions of her peers: "They are not working, they are not forced to do the videos, their parents only care about them and they want them to have fun" [FG4B.1: 37:22].

Finally, we would like to remark that pupils lacked knowledge in relation to other issues. For example, when they were asked about who owns YouTube, they were unaware that it belongs to Google and that indirectly a price is paid for this service through the surrendering of our private data. They did seem to be conscious of the fact that when different people search on YouTube, search results can differ, but they did not understand exactly why.

What are these children's processes of interaction with YouTubers like and how do they read *Las Ratitas'* videos?

In each sub-group of all the focus group there were pupils who demonstrated negotiated and oppositional readings to the content of *Las Ratitas'* videos. From year 1 upwards, many were quite critical about some of the countervalues that they felt were transmitted in these videos, showing media competence regarding the underlined ideology attached to these media products. Thus, in relation to the video *McDonalds con mi coche drive thru*, there were critical voices about the unhealthiest of fast food, saying that it has too much fat and sugar: "If you eat a lot of this food, you have belly pains" [FG1.2B: 26:07]; in relation to the video *Morning routine*, many criticised a scene where the youngest sister was imitating the cat in the app and was throwing

the toilet paper on the floor: “That’s crazy, who wastes toilet paper like this? They cut down trees and we run out of oxygen” [FG3.1B 23:12]. Example of some other countervalues detected in both videos refer to the use of too much plastic; placing the baby doll in the front seat of the car; hurting the cat; having breakfast and cleaning your teeth while you are watching the tablet. Some 6th year pupils also referred to countervalues in other videos from the channel: “They threw a mobile phone into the pool, just to get views because a mobile phone is expensive [...], laughing when they throw the phone into the pool when many people are poor” [FG6.2B: 31:45].

However, pupils from each year focused their attention on the videos and even laughed on occasions. First year pupils openly affirmed they liked the video and they found it funny, while also being less critical of the messages. In contrast, pupils from higher years ridiculed *Las Ratitas*’ videos while at the same time defended their favourite influencers by way of saying that they were not fake and that they let followers know what they advertise [FG6.1B 21:13; FG3.1A 37:05].

It is important to remark that when the pupils were asked if these kidfluencers would make the same video if they were boys, many said no, they would not. Many were of the opinion that they would do videos of videogames, or that the story would be different. As previously mentioned, we perceived gender-biased consumption trends and we also perceived them in the negotiation of meanings, with more boys than girls showing oppositional visions, especially in the lower year groups, whilst in the higher year groups both boys and girls were similarly critical of the videos and the channel.

DISCUSSION

The main aims of this study were listening to children in order to understand the digital content that forms an influential part of their daily lives, as well as analysing the media competence they show and the ways they interact and negotiate meanings with *Las Ratitas* and other favourite influencers.

The dialogues that took place during the focus groups leave no doubt that with most of these primary pupils, digital content and social media consumption not only begins at a very early age but occupies a substantial amount of time in their daily lives. In addition, it is an individualistic activity performed on devices such as tablets (De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019; Jaakkola, 2020; Jihea Ahn, 2022). Many children know

and follow a multitude of YouTubers, their consumption of these influencers’ channels is clearly based on gender (Castillo-Abdul, Romero-Rodríguez & Larrea-Ayala, 2020; Ward & Grower, 2020), and they rapidly move to more adult content and other social media platforms as they grow up. Despite the dialogues showing that they knew *Las Ratitas* and confirmed that they used to follow them when they were in infant education, there was the assumption among them that *Las Ratitas* were for smaller kids and were justly ridiculed for this reason. Moreover, it was observed that a substantial number of the pupils follow YouTubers and Streamers for young adults.

The Internet enables children to access information and content that can be unsuitable for their age. Children can be exposed to an adult world before they are developmentally ready and can normalise some problematic realities (Bishop, 2022). The pressure on children to be adult-like quickly has long been happening, during the industrial revolution children were turned into economically profitable subjects and today’s neoliberal policies and managerialism represent a continuation. Converting children into adult-like consumers brings benefits to large corporations and the long temporality they represent can produce abundant benefits (Bousfield & Ragusa, 2014; Steinberg, 2011). The omnipresence of ICT in our digital society could be seen as having an important role in this phenomenon of growing up too quickly (Bishop, 2022; Brown, Thornton & Sutterby, 2004). As Postman (1994) had already anticipated, the rise of electronic media would blur the boundaries between childhood and adulthood, arguing that children would be increasingly exposed to the same images and ideas as adults are. However, this notion of children getting older younger is not free from controversy, as we will refer below.

Having listened to the pupils, it can be affirmed that media competence clearly depends on children’s developmental stages, as the youngest children in the focus groups showed more difficulties processing and expressing the intentions behind *Las Ratitas*’ videos. In relation to advertising, previous research has demonstrated that, for children under the age of twelve, advertising literacy is not fully developed. They do not have the ability to cognitively understand the persuasive strategies, to control their emotions or to evaluate the fairness of advertising (De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019). In addition, influencer marketing and its product placement and product integration techniques, clearly used in *Las Ratitas*’ videos, make children more vulnerable to the promotion of a consumerist lifestyle

(Pearce & Baran, 2018). However, in the focus groups, when children's attention was directed at some products and brands embedded in the content, many children showed a clear understanding of the role of influencers as endorsers and took a critical stand. It must be mentioned that previous studies have shown that children's understanding of celebrity endorsement seems to be developed earlier than their ability to detect other advertising techniques (Rozendaal, Buijzen & Valkenburg, 2011). The focus groups proved that, as Rasmussen, Riggs and Sauermilch (2021) state, children can benefit from conversations with educators about influencers and these conversations can encourage and promote their critical thinking, whilst mitigating potentially negative effects of social media consumption. Moreover, the fact that in both of the 1st year focus groups a few pupils showed unexpectedly good advertising literacy skills could indicate that their parents engage in concept-oriented communication and active mediation in relation to media at home (Jihea Ahn, 2022; Pearce & Baran, 2018).

Influencers and kidfluencers will usually make a point of targeting their own age group and they follow similar ways of engaging with their audience, aimed at establishing a relationship of closeness and trust with their followers (Castillo-Abdul, Romero-Rodríguez & Larrea-Ayala, 2020; Márquez & Ardévol, 2018; Pérez-Torres, Pastor-Ruiz & Abarrou-Ben-Boubaker, 2018). Moreover, previous studies have demonstrated that children engage in peer modelling when the peer is the same age group or a bit older (De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019). Children get involved and participate in parasocial interactions with their favourite kidfluencers (De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019), developing an emotional connection of wishful identification (Tolbert & Drogos, 2019). Therefore, it was expected that the popular channel *Las Ratitas*, starring two sisters, aged 9 and 11, would be part of these primary education pupils' leisure time on screens. However, the dialogues in the focus groups did not confirm this prediction and even though many children avowed that they knew these girls and used to watch their videos, and despite showing enjoyment and being very attentive during the reproduction of the videos in the focus groups, many pupils ridiculed them and expressed that they were for little kids. Only a few children seemed to have an ongoing strong parasocial relationship with *Las Ratitas*. The reasons for this finding could be related to the previously mentioned attraction to young adult content and the gender-biased consumption of media. In most of all the different aged focus groups, there were more boys

than girls openly making derogatory comments about *Las Ratitas*' videos (Schroeder & Liben, 2020; Ward & Grower, 2020). However, this tendency to ridicule these videos also resulted in the pupils emotionally distancing themselves from the messages, which seemed to favour their ability to analyse them more critically, showing negotiated and oppositional readings (Hall, 2006). On the contrary, those pupils who show greater emotional attachment to these kidfluencers show more susceptibility to their persuasive messages (Rasmussen, Riggs & Sauermilch, 2021).

Taking into account the observed negotiated and oppositional readings upon the reception of these kidfluencers' messages, we must draw attention to the fact that many of these children were quite critical about the commercial nature, persuasive intent and deceitful tactics used in the videos. They also referred to the unethical reproduction of stereotypes and questioned the exposure, and possible exploitation of these girls. Moreover, they were critical of some of the countervalues transmitted. They highlighted *Las Ratitas*' misleading and disrespectful attitude towards current environmental concerns and poverty, in addition to the way they incite the consumption of unhealthy products. Furthermore, it could be seen that there were leaders among the participating children who overtly expressed their strong opinions in order to demonstrate knowledge, thereby winning the acceptance of their peers, who in turn repeated the same arguments. Either way, we were surprised by their arguments and maturity, which went against our expectations and even some previous studies (De Veirman, Hudders & Nelson, 2019). This situation shows that ICT can both facilitate access to inappropriate content for children and foster their opportunities to learn in community. ICT can help children build knowledge and enable them to think critically, as long as it is conceived as an empowering and participatory digital tool (Cabero-Almenara, Torres-Barzabal & Hermosilla-Rodríguez, 2019). However, technology should not be seen as the only thing responsible for children's developmental rhythms. In fact, there are voices that question whether kids are indeed getting older younger, arguing, instead, that existing intensive parenting is making children stay young longer (Bishop, 2022).

In any case, the negotiated and oppositional readings observed in the focus groups are unlikely to happen with infant education children, who seem to be the main consumers of this channel. While their parents may feel secure whilst keeping them occupied watching *Las Ratitas* on YouTube Kids (De Veirman, Hudders &

Nelson, 2019; Jaakkola, 2020), their children are subjected to covert advertising and to the values of an artificial and happy world where needs and problems are both covered and solved respectively by way of material objects, and where women occupy a role in accordance with the values of a patriarchal society (Digón Regueiro, Rodríguez Guimerans & Castro Rodríguez, 2023).

Lastly, we cannot finish this section without recognising the possibility that some of the children's spoken observations may have been articulated to suit what was expected in the school context. In addition, it also remains to be seen whether they would be able to transfer this ability of critical analysis to the messages transmitted by their favourite YouTubers and influencers. Nonetheless, the importance of creating these spaces for dialogue and reflection on children's media consumption, and the relevance of listening to them to really understand what they know, feel and think, should be emphasised (Jihea Ahn, 2022).

CONCLUSIONS

Children's overexposure to screens takes away time from their real life and denies them opportunities to connect with real-world relevance through experiential learning and playing, which is an essential childhood need. There are numerous studies that have already warned of the danger of misusing screens. Thus, the psychiatrist Serge Tisseron (2013) created the 3-6-9-12 rule in which it is recommended not to use screens before the age of 3, not to use video consoles before the age of 6, not to use the Internet before the age of 9, and to have guided use of the Internet from the age of 12⁷. Moderate use and proper guidance by adults are essential if we want technologies to contribute positively rather than negatively to children's development.

Parents need be aware that the conditioning processes exercised by social media work subtly and efficiently on children, moulding them into young and long-term consumers. Kidfluencers arouse in their followers the desire to live according to fictions. Such desires, referring to both having and being, are strengthened to the point of rendering followers' daily lives as mediocre, bland, boring and unsatisfactory. These YouTubers are basically an essential tool of the market, capable of generating fictitious needs and

thereby hiding real ones, which are, of course, less economically profitable.

We need schools committed to developing children's critical digital and media literacy, whilst also helping to develop these competences in those adults who are part of the educational community. Such schools should promote processes of emancipation in children and spread the importance of media literacy education outside the school. In this study, we have seen how the participating school introduced media literacy as part of its educational activities, turning media products into objects of study and encouraging critical reflection. This initiative can thus be expanded to households, thereby encouraging parents to take an interest in questioning what their children consume. Research findings, such as those outlined in this article, can provide inspiration for practitioners and educators seeking to foster media literacy education and critical thinking in their classrooms. The use of a scripted questionnaire, grounded on a well-articulated framework of media competence dimensions and indicators, could serve as a valuable tool for guiding the introduction of critical media analysis in educational settings.

It is important for further research to continue studying children's opinions about their use of ICT and media. The documenting of children's lives and their relationship with screens by using research methods such as focus groups positions children as active principal actors and is tremendously illuminating and eye-opening. In terms of the limitations of this study, it is essential to recognise that while the selected videos featured popular kidfluencers, there may have been variations in findings had we utilised content from their preferred influencers or incorporated material from boy influencers. Certain comments from the children prompt us to question that this may be the case. In addition, the school context and the presence of teachers may have had an influence on the dialogues that took place in the focus groups. It is worth mentioning the impact of the focus group's size, which was influenced by the teachers' desire to involve all students in fostering media literacy education. This decision had both advantages and disadvantages. On the positive side, it underscored the school's commitment to media literacy education, resulting in a post on the school blog featuring reflections and pertinent information targeted at students and their families. Moreover, this post may

⁷ See <https://www.3-6-9-12.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/flyer-apprivoiser-les-ecrans-2018-anglais2-hr.pdf>

have sparked interest in similar topics among other schools. However, there were challenges associated with this approach. Researchers and teachers had to meticulously manage the focus groups, ensuring the participation of all attendees while fostering constructive dialogues and debates among them. Nevertheless, despite the challenges and considerations mentioned, the overriding goal of this project, namely, investigating the ways in which children interact with social media and articulating learning environments at the service of critical digital and media literacy, was duly achieved.

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REFERENCES

- Aran-Ramspott, S., Fedele, M., & Tarragó, A. (2018). YouTubers' social functions and their influence on pre-adolescence. *Comunicar*, 57, 71-80. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C57-2018-07>
- Aznar Díaz, I., Trujillo Torres, J. M., & Romero Rodríguez, J. M. (2019). Kids YouTubers generation: analysis of YouTube channels of the new child phenomena. *Pixel-bit*, 56, 113-129. <https://doi.org/10.12795/pixelbit.2019.i56.06>
- Bishop, K. (24 March 2022). Kids getting older younger: Are children growing up too fast? *BBC*. <https://www.bbc.com/worklife/article/20220324-kgoy-kids-getting-older-younger>
- Bousfield, K., & Ragusa, A.T. (2014) A sociological analysis of Australia's NAPLAN and My School Senate Inquiry submissions: the adultification of childhood? *Critical Studies in Education*, 55(2), 170-185. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17508487.2013.877051>
- Bourne, J., & Winstone, N. (2021). Empowering pupils' voices: the use of activity-oriented focus groups in higher education research. *International Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 44(4), 352-365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1743727X.2020.1777964>
- Brown, P. S., Thornton, C. D., & Sutterby, J. A. (2004). Kids getting older younger: The Adultification of Children's Play in R.L. Clements & I. Fiorentino (Eds.) *The Child's Right to Play. A Global Approach* (pp. 177-185). Praeger Publishers.
- Buckingham, D. (2011). *The material child: Growing up in consumer culture*. Cambridge Polity.
- Buijzen, M., Van Reijmersdal, E. A., & Owen, L. H. (2010). Introducing the PCMC Model: An Investigative Framework for Young People's Processing of Commercialized Media Content, *Communication Theory*, 20, 427-450. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2885.2010.01370.x>
- Cabero-Almenara, J., Torres-Barzabal, L., & Hermosilla-Rodríguez, J. M. (2019). Las TIC y la creación de una ciudadanía crítica e-digital, *Education in the Knowledge Society*, 20, 1-10. https://doi.org/10.14201/eks2019_20_a22
- Castillo-Abdul, B., Romero-Rodríguez, L.M., & Larrea-Ayala, A. (2020). Kid influencers in Spain: understanding the themes they address and preteens' engagement with their YouTube channels. *Heliyon*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05056>
- Choi, E. (2023). Brand Integration, Disclosure, and Ethics in Child-Targeted YouTube Videos: A Content Analysis, *Journal of Media Ethics*, 38(1), 34-47, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23736992.2022.2158829>
- De Veirman, M., Hudders, L., & Nelson, M. R. (2019). What Is Influencer Marketing and How Does It Target Children? *A Review and Direction for Future Research*. *Front. Psychol*, 10, 2685. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02685>
- Digón Regueiro, P., Rodríguez Guimerans, A., & Castro Rodríguez, M. M. (2023). Menores influencers y la importancia de una alfabetización mediática crítica. *EDMETIC*, 12(1), art.7. <https://doi.org/10.21071/edmetic.v12i1.15223>
- Evans, N. J., Hoy, M. G., & Childers, C. C. (2018) Parenting "YouTube Natives": The Impact of Pre-Roll Advertising and Text Disclosures on Parental Responses to Sponsored Child Influencer Videos, *Journal of Advertising*, 47(4), 326-346. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2018.1544952>
- Ferrés, J., & Piscitelli, A. (2012). Media Competence. Articulated Proposal of Dimensions and Indicators, *Comunicar*, 38, 75-82. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3916/C38-2012-02-08>
- Hall, S. (2006). 'Encoding/decoding' in M.G. Durham and D.M. Kellner (Eds.) *Media and Cultural Studies. Keywords* (revised edition, pp. 163-173). Blackwell Publishing.

- Hennink, M. M. (2007). *International Focus Group Research A Handbook for the Health and Social Sciences*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511619458>
- Jaakkola, M. (2020). From vernacularized commercialism to kidbait: toy review videos on YouTube and the problematics of the mash-up genre, *Journal of Children and Media*, 14(2), 237-254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482798.2019.1693409>
- Jihea Ahn, R. (2022). Exploration of Parental Advertising Literacy and Parental Mediation: Influencer Marketing of Media Character Toy and Merchandise, *Journal of Advertising*, 51(1), 107-115, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2021.1944935>
- Jordan, A., & Klein, N. (2020). Branding, privacy, and identity: growing up in surveillance capitalism, *Journal of Children and Media*, 14(2), 259-266. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482798.2020.1735148>
- Jorge, A., Marôpo, L., & Nunes, T. (2018). 'I am not being sponsored to say this': a teen YouTuber and her audience negotiate branded content. Observatorio (OBS), *Special issue on The co-option of audiences in the attention economy*. <http://obs.obercom.pt/index.php/obs/article/view/1382/pdf>
- Livingstone, S. (Jan 28, 2020). *Can we realise children's rights in a digital world? A provocation paper*. The British Academy. <https://medium.com/reframing-childhood-past-and-present/can-we-realise-childrens-rights-in-a-digital-world-d4f5f19f298f>
- López-Villafranca, P., & Olmedo-Salar, S. (2019). Menores en YouTube, ¿ocio o negocio? Análisis de casos en España y EUA. *El profesional de la información*, 28(5), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2019.sep.20>
- Lupton, D., & Williamson, B. (2017). The datafied child: The dataveillance of children and implication for their rights, *New media and society*, 19(5), 780-794. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444816686328>
- Márquez, I., & Ardèvol, E. (2018). Hegemonía y contrahegemonía en el fenómeno YouTuber. *Desacatos*, 56, 34-49.
- Marôpo, L., Jorge, A., & Tomaz, R. (2020). "I felt like I was really talking to you!": intimacy and trust among teen vloggers and followers in Portugal and Brazil, *Journal of Children and Media*, 14(1), 22-37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482798.2019.1699589>
- Martínez, C., & Olsson, T. (2019). Making sense of YouTubers: how Swedish children construct and negotiate the YouTuber Misslisibell as a girl celebrity, *Journal of Children and Media*, 13(1), 36-52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482798.2018.1517656>
- Núñez-Cansado, M., López-López, A., & Somarriba-Arechavala, N. (2021). Publicidad encubierta en los kidsfluencers. Una propuesta metodológica aplicada al estudio de caso de los diez YouTubers menores con más seguidores de España, *Profesional de la información*, 30(2). <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2021.mar.19>
- Palatino, B. (2020). *La civilización de la memoria de pez: Pequeño tratado sobre el mercado de la atención*. Alianza Editorial.
- Parker, A., & Tritter, J. (2006). Focus group method and methodology: current practice and recent debate, *International Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 29(1), 23-37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01406720500537304>
- Pearce, K. J., & Baran, S. (2018). Foregrounding Morality: Encouraging Parental Media Literacy Intervention Using the TARES Test for Ethical Persuasion, *Journal of Media Literacy Education*, 10(3), 57-79. <https://doi.org/10.23860/JMLE-2018-10-3-4>
- Pérez-Torres, V., Pastor-Ruiz, Y., & Abarrou-Ben-Boubaker, S. (2018). YouTubers videos and the construction of adolescent identity. *Comunicar*, 55, 61-70. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C55-2018-06>
- Postman, N. (1994). *The disappearance of childhood*. Vintage/Random House.
- Quostodio (2023). *From Alpha to Zeta: raising the digital generations*. https://static.quostodio.com/public-site/uploads/2023/02/06151022/ADR_2023_en.pdf
- Rasmussen, E. E., Riggs, R. E., & Sauermilch, W.S. (2021). Kidfluencer exposure, materialism, and U.S. tweens' purchase of sponsored products, *Journal of Children and Media*, 16(1), 68-77. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482798.2021.1910053>
- Renés Arellano, P., Gozávez Pérez, V., & Berlanga Fernández, I. (2020). YouTube and influencers in childhood. Content analysis and educational proposals, *Icono 14*, 18(2), 269-295. <https://doi.org/10.7195/ri14.v18i2.1455>
- Rozendaal, E., Buijzen, M., & Valkenburg, P. (2011). Children's understanding of advertisers' persuasive tactics, *Int. J. Advert.* 30, 329-350. <https://doi.org/10.2501/IJA-30-2-329-350>
- Sánchez-Labela Martín, I. (2020). YouTubers infantiles: los menores como recurso para generar

- nuevas tendencias publicitarias, *Austral Comunicación* 9(2), 249-274.
<https://doi.org/10.26422/aucom.2020.0902.san>
- Schroeder, K. M., & Liben, L.S. (2020). Felt Pressure to Conform to Cultural Gender Roles: Correlates and Consequences, *Sex Roles*, 84, 125-138, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-020-01155-9>
- Steinberg, S. (2011). *Kinderculture: The Corporate Construction of Childhood*. Routledge, 3rd Edition.
- Tisseron, S. (2013). *3-6-9-12, apprivoiser les écrans et grandir*. Éres.
- Tolbert, A. N., & Drogos, K. L. (2019). Tweens' Wishful Identification and Parasocial Relationships With YouTubers. *Front. Psychol*, 10(2781), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02781>
- Tur-Viñes, V., Núñez-Gómez, P., & Martínez-Pastor, E. (2019). YouTube, menores y cultura colaborativa. Revisión bibliográfica de la investigación académica, *Historia y comunicación social* 24(1), 331-351. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5209/HICS.64498>
- Vizcaíno-Laorga, R., Martínez Pastor, E., & Serrano Maíllo, I. (2019). Just Within the Limits of the Law: Minors from Consumers of Advertising to Creators of Advertising in Spain. *KOME-An International Journal of Pure Communication Inquiry*, 7(1), 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.17646/KOME.75698.99>
- Ward, L. A., & Grower, P. (2020). Media and the Development of Gender Role Stereotypes. *Annu. Rev. Dev. Psychol.* 2, 177-99. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-devpsych-051120-010630>